

AP-1 activation in suicide and maternal behavior.

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We recently described a basic oxytocin signaling component in the brain in human suicide. Here we demonstrate using whole transcriptome sequencing in humans that AP-1 signaling in the mammalian brain, which controls maternal-type nurturing behaviors between the mother and the infant like nursing, is a gene product of interest in conferring risk for suicide completion in humans. Together the data indicated that circuitry and signaling in the brain governing basic essential features of the female, and its dysfunction, were intrinsically linked with suicide.

Citations

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